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Characteristics Property of a P -Disconnected Topological Space

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Abstract:

In this paper we present definitions, examples and important results about connected and disconnected topological spaces. We also present connected and disconnected topological concepts in terms of some generalized concepts such as p -open, s -open, g -open, etc sets. We investigate the most important characteristics property of a p -disconnected, s -disconnected and g -disconnected. We have generalized versions of main results.

Keywords: Disconnection p -open, p -disconnected, s -open, g -open, s -disconnected, g -disconnected.

§1. Preliminaries:

First of all, we mention preliminary definitions and results for easy reference.

Definition (1.1): Let (X, T) be a topological space. A disconnection of X is a pair (A, B) of non-empty disjoint open subsets of X whose union is X . The space X is said to be connected if there does not exist a disconnection of X .

A topological space X is said to be disconnected if there exists a disconnection of X .

A disconnected space is characterized as follows:

Theorem (1.1): Let (X, T) be a topological space. Then X is disconnected iff there exists a non-empty proper subset A of X which is simultaneously open and closed.

This means that in a connected topological space ϕ and X are its only subsets which are simultaneously open and closed.

Another characteristic property of a disconnected space is as follows:

Theorem (1.2): Let (X, T) be a topological space. Then X is disconnected iff there exist a continuous mapping of X onto the discrete two point space $Y = \{0, 1\}$.

Definition (1.2): A subset Y of a topological space (X, T) is said to be disconnected if there exist two non-empty open sets G and H in X such that

- (i) $Y \subseteq G \cup H$
- (ii) $Y \cap G, Y \cap H$ are non-empty
- (iii) $(Y \cap G) \cap (Y \cap H) = \phi$

A subset Y of X is said to be connected iff it is not disconnected.

Some important properties of connected sets are as follows:

Theorem (1.3): Let (X, T) be a topological space. Let $\{A_i\}$ be a non-empty family of connected subsets of X such that $\bigcap A_i \neq \phi$. Then

$$A = \bigcup A_i \text{ is also a connected subset of } X.$$

Theorem (1.4): Let (X, T) be a topological space and let A be a connected subset of X . Let B be a subset of X such that $A \subseteq B \subseteq \text{cl } A$. Then B is connected.

Corollary (1.1): Let (X, T) be a topological space and let A be a connected subset of X . Then $\text{cl } A$ is also a connected subset of X .

Example (1.1): An indiscrete topological space (X, T) is connected.

Example (1.2): A discrete topological space (X, T) with at least two points is disconnected.

Example (1.3): The empty set ϕ and every singleton subset of a topological space (X, T) are connected.

Example (1.4): Let (X, T) be a topological space where $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $T = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$.

If we put $A = \{a, b\}$ and $B = \{c, d\}$. Then $A \cup B = X$ is a disconnection of X . Hence (X, T) is disconnected.

Example (1.5): Let (X, T) be a topological space where $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $T = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$.

Since ϕ and X are the only open and closed sets in (X, T) , the space is connected.

§2. Characteristics Property of a P -Disconnected Topological Space:

Here we discuss the concepts of connected and disconnected topological spaces in terms of some generalized topological concepts such as p -open, s -open, g -open, etc sets.

Definition (2.1): Let (X, T) be a topological space. A p -disconnection (resp., s -disconnection, g -disconnection) of X is a pair (A, B) of non-empty disjoint p -open (resp., s -open, g -open) subsets of X whose union is X .

The space X is said to be p -connected (resp., s -connected, g -connected) if there does not exist a p -disconnection (resp., s -disconnection, g -disconnection) of X .

A p -disconnected space is characterized as follows:

Theorem (2.1): Let (X, T) be a topological space. Then X is p -disconnected iff there exist a non-empty proper subset of X which is simultaneously p -open and p -closed.

Proof: Let A be non-empty proper subset of X which is both p -open and p -closed. Then we have to show that X is p -disconnected. Let $B = A^c$. Then B is non-empty, proper p -open and p -closed subset of X . Also $A \cup B = X$ and $A \cap B = \phi$. Thus we get a p -disconnection of X . So X is p -disconnected.

Conversely, Let X be p -disconnected. Then there exist non-empty disjoint p -open subsets A and B of X such that $A \cup B = X$. This means that $A = B'$. Since B is non-empty and p -open, A is a proper p -closed subset of X . In other words, there exist a proper subset A of X which is simultaneously p -open and p -closed. Hence the result.

Note (2.1): Similar results can be proved for s -disconnected and g -disconnected spaces.

Note (2.2): In a p -connected (resp., s -connected, g -connected) topological spaces ϕ and X are its only subsets which are simultaneously p -open and p -closed (resp., s -open and s -closed, g -open and g -closed).

Note (2.3): It is important to note that if X is disconnected. Then it is p -disconnected, s -disconnected, α -disconnected and β -disconnected.

However all these concepts are different. This can be seen through different examples.

Example (2.1): Every indiscrete space with more than one element is connected but it is p -disconnected because every subset of an indiscrete space is p -open and p -closed.

Example (2.2): Let (X, T) be a topological space where $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $T = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$.

Then closed subsets of X are $\phi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X$.

Here (X, T) is a connected topological space.

Now p -open and α -open subsets of X are $\{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$ which coincides with T .

So X is connected, p -connected and α -connected.

Again s -open subsets and β -open subsets of X are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X$.

Since $X = \{a, c\} \cup \{b, d\}$ is a s -disconnection of X , X is s -disconnected and β -disconnected space.

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